

The amperometric method exhibits many advantages than the other titrimetric methods. Since permanganate is reduced at almost zero applied e.m.f., deaeration of the solution containing the reducible material is not necessary. Furthermore the amperometric method is more rapid and simple, where the equivalent point can be determined from few readings before and after the end point. Therefore, the amperometric method can be considered as a good analytical tool for determining amounts of sodium nitrite as low as 6.9 μg , whereas the lower amount determined by the potentiometric method was 0.093 mg⁸.

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Synthesis of I-5, II-5, I-7, II-7-Tetramethoxy [I-8, II-8] Biflavone

P. GANDHI & R. D. TIWARI

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad,
Allahabad-211002

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ONE of the common methods employed for the synthesis of various naturally occurring biflavonoids^{1,2} is simple or crossed Ullmann reaction²⁻⁶. Generally the dimers are obtained in low yields.

I-5, II-5, I-7, II-7-Tetramethoxy [I-8, II-8] biflavone has now been synthesised from the corresponding biphenyl derivatives. The mono iodination of xanthoxylin gave 2-hydroxy-3-iodo-4,6-dimethoxyacetophenone⁷ (I). This underwent reaction with copper bronze at 280° to give 2,2'-dihydroxy-4,4', 6,6'-tetramethoxy-3,3'-diacetylbi-phenyl (IIa) (ν_{max} 1630 cm^{-1}). The compound (IIa) on benzylation gave 2,2'-dibenzoyloxy-4,4', 6,6'-tetramethoxy-3,3'-diacetylbi-phenyl (IIb) (ν_{max} 1690 cm^{-1}), which underwent rearrangement when heated with acetone and potassium carbonate to give 4,4', 6,6'-tetramethoxy-2,2'-dihydroxy-3,3'-di(ω -benzoyl acetyl)= biphenyl (IIc) (ν_{max} 1630 and 1690 cm^{-1}). On acid cyclisation this gave an almost quantitative yield of the biflavone (III) (ν_{max} 1645 cm^{-1}). In the mass spectrum of (III) the molecular ion appeared at m/e 562 and the general

fragmentation pattern was typical of a C-C linked biflavone⁸

(III)

- (a) R = CH₃; R₁ = H; R₂ = OCH₃
 (b) R = CH₃; R₁ = COC₆H₅; R₂ = OCH₃
 (c) R = CH₂COC₆H₅; R₁ = COC₆H₅; R₂ = OCH₃

Experimental

(a) 2,2'-Dihydroxy-4,4', 6,6'-tetramethoxy-3,3'-diacetylbi-phenyl

A mixture of 2-hydroxy-3-iodo-4,6-dimethoxyacetophenone (5 g), copper bronze (15 g) and dimethyl formamide (100 ml) was refluxed in a metal bath for 4 hr, filtered hot and washed with 15 ml of solvent. Water (200 ml) was added to the combined filtrate and washings and left overnight. The precipitate was filtered and recrystallised from dimethylformamide=water as colourless needles, m.p. 185°-186° (found: C, 61.3; H, 5.56; Mol. wt. (Rast method), 372; C₂₀H₂₂O₈ requires C, 61.53; H, 5.64%; mol. wt., 390).

(b) 4,4', 6,6'-Tetramethoxy-2,2'-dibenzoyloxy-3,3'-diacetylbi-phenyl

A mixture of 4,4', 6,6'-tetramethoxy-2,2'-dihydroxy-3,3'-diacetylbi-phenyl (11.8 g), benzoyl chloride (8.4 g) and pyridine (30 ml) was heated on steam bath for 15 min, poured into water and stirred with dil. HCl and then with dilute alcohol. After it had solidified the product was washed with dilute alcohol, dried at room temperature and crystallised from alcohol=water as colourless plates, m.p. 78°-79° (found: C, 67.65; H, 5.1; C₃₁H₃₀O₁₀ requires C, 68.23; H, 5.02%).

(c) 4,4', 6,6'-Tetramethoxy-2,2'-dihydroxy-3,3'-di(ω -benzoylacetyl)-biphenyl

A mixture of 4,4', 6,6'-tetramethoxy-2,2'-dibenzoyloxy-3,3'-diacetyl biphenyl (5 g), acetone (200 ml) and potassium carbonate (50 g) was refluxed on a water bath for 30 hr. Acetone was removed by distillation on water bath. The residue was added to water. The precipitated 4,4', 6,6'-tetramethoxy-2,2'-dihydroxy-3,3'-di(ω -benzoylacetyl)-biphenyl was filtered and recrystallised from dilute alcohol as yellow needles, m.p. 178°–179° (found: C, 67.86; H, 4.95; $C_{34}H_{30}O_{10}$ requires C, 68.23; H, 5.017%).

(d) I-5, II-5, I-7, II-7-Tetramethoxy [I-8, II-8] biflavone

4,4', 6,6'-tetramethoxy-2,2'-dihydroxy-3,3'-di(ω -benzoylacetyl)-biphenyl (2 g) was dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid (20 ml) and kept at room temperature. After 8 hr the solution was poured into water. The precipitated biflavone was filtered and recrystallised from dilute alcohol as yellow needles, m.p. 203°–204°, λ_{max} in ethanol at 270 and 310 nm. (Found: C, 72.35; H, 4.55; OMe, 21.2; Mol. wt. (Mass spectrometry), 562; $C_{34}H_{28}O_8$ requires C, 72.61; H, 4.63; OMe, 22.07%; Mol. wt., 562).

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Chemical Investigation of *Canthium diococcum*

KABERI MUKHERJEE

Botanical Survey of India, Indian Museum, Calcutta

&

LATIKA BOSE

Rammohan College, Calcutta

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THE benzene extract of the bark of the plant *Canthium diococcum* after column chromatography yielded a number of terpenoids. One of these compounds, $C_{30}H_{50}O$, m.p. 185°–86°, formed

an acetate, $C_{32}H_{52}O_2$, m.p. 225°, and these have been characterized as α -amyrin and its acetate respectively by comparison of m.p., TLC and IR spectra with authentic samples. The alcoholic extract of the bark yielded a saponin which on acid hydrolysis gave an acid, $C_{30}H_{48}O_3$, m.p. 306°–8°, which formed a methyl ester, $C_{31}H_{50}O_3$, m.p. 196°–8°. These have been characterized as oleanolic acid and methyl oleanolate respectively by comparison of m.p., TLC and IR spectra with authentic samples.

Experimental

Air-dried powdered bark (1 kg) was extracted successively with benzene and ethanol (95%) for 48 hr in a Soxhlet apparatus. The benzene extract was separated into acid and neutral fractions in the usual way and the latter was subjected to column chromatography over silica gel (200 g) and eluted with different solvents. Benzene eluate gave a fraction which was crystallized from ethanol, $C_{30}H_{50}O$, m.p. 185°–86°. It was heated with acetic anhydride and pyridine on steam bath and worked up in the usual way. Crystallization from ethanol gave an acetate, $C_{32}H_{52}O_2$, m.p. 225°.

The ethanolic extract was concentrated by distillation and the crude saponin was precipitated by addition of excess ether. The crude saponin gave copious lather when shaken with water. It was dissolved in ethanol (200 ml) and 40 ml of conc. hydrochloric acid was added and refluxed on steam bath for an hour. This was then diluted with water and the precipitated sapogenin was extracted with ether which was separated into acid and neutral fractions in the usual way with 1% aqueous caustic potash solution. The acid fraction was chromatographed over silica gel and the $CHCl_3/MeOH$ (95:5 v/v) eluate gave a fraction which crystallized from methanol, $C_{31}H_{50}O_3$, m.p. 196°–8°.

Satisfactory analytical data were obtained for the compounds reported.

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Triterpenoids. XLII. Further Studies on the Structure of Lantanolic Acid

A. K. BARUA, MISS P. CHAKRABARTI, K. BASU, A. BASAK, S. CHAKRAVARTI & S. K. BANERJEE*

Department of Chemistry, Bose Institute, Calcutta-9

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BARUA and co-workers earlier^{1,2} proposed the structure (I) for lantanolic acid, a new triterpene

* St. Xavier's College, Calcutta.